

Effect of Stress on Glucose Metabolism

Ashish Shrivastava and H. K. Garg*

Department of Biotechnology,
C.S.A. Govt. P. G. Nodal College, Sehore - 466 001 (India)

*Department of Zoology and Biotechnology,
Govt. Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal - 462008 (India)

Diabetes mellitus is a set of disorders that share common insufficiency in the regulation of carbohydrate metabolism. The term diabetes mellitus refers to the sweet tang urine of patients with the disease, a symptom first described by Areteus over 2000 years ago. Stress has long been suspected as a prime cause of metabolic disarray. Stress impairs glucose metabolism by discharging a host of 'counter-regulatory' hormones that result in declined insulin activity and elevated blood glucose levels.

Stress has an energy mobilizing effect on a healthy organism. However, in patients suffering from diabetes, due to relative or absolute lack of insulin, stress provoked high blood glucose cannot be adequately metabolized. Thus, stress is a potential contributor to chronic hyperglycemia in diabetes. Bjorntorp (1991) suggested that this mechanism may lead to both central obesity and a predisposition to diabetes. Stress initiated discharge of growth hormone and beta-endorphin can also reduce glucose uptake, restrain insulin secretion and raise glucose levels. There are vagal afferents from the liver to the central nervous system and brain receptors for numerous peptide hormones originally found in gut. The adaptive benefit of the mechanism of stress-induced energy mobilization in healthy individuals is evident, but in diabetic individuals, where glucose metabolism is on stake, the mechanism may be complicated.

Keywords: Glucose metabolism, Diabetes mellitus, Stress-induced energy mobilization.

References:

- **Garg, HK;** Choudhary, A; Shrivastava, A (2014) Allicin as a potential inducer of apoptosis in cancer cells-I. *National Conference on Recent Updates in Biological Research*, 19.
- **Garg, HK;** Choudhary, A (2015) Allicin as a potential inducer of apoptosis in cancer cells-II. *National Seminar on Recent Trends in Science & Technology*, 65.
- **Garg, HK;** Choudhary, A (2011) Anticancer & Anti mutagenic Properties of Medicinal Plants. *National Seminar On Emerging Trends In Biodiversity & Environmental Conservation*, 39.
- **Garg, HK;** Garg, J (2013) Should labeling be enforced on genetically designed products? *National Seminar on Computer Assisted Drug Designing for Green Chemistry*, 20-21.

- **Garg, HK;** Garg, J (2013) Consternations over genetically designed products. *National Seminar on Computer Assisted Drug Designing for Green Chemistry*, 23-24.
- **Garg, HK;** Garg, J (2012) Worldwide Endorsement on Genetically Modified Food. *National Seminar on Science for Shaping the Future of India* organized under the auspices of Indian Science Congress Kolkata & M.P. Council of Science & Technology Bhopal, 68.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A; Choudhary, A (2015) Flavonoids from Lemon & Tea as Effective Inhibitors against Carcinogenesis. *National Seminar on Innovations in Science & Technology for Inclusive Development*, 08.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Andrographolide induced succinate dehydrogenase activity in isolated mitochondrial fractions from different organ of BALB/c mice. International Organization for Scientific Research - **Journal of Pharmacy & Biological Sciences**, USA 6(4) : 43-45.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Evaluation and impact of anti-tuberculosis drug. **International Journal of Scientific Research**, 2(7): 20-21.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Clinical use of andrographolide as a potential drug against vole tuberculosis. **International Journal of Pure & Applied Zoology**, USA 1(3) 223-226.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Allicin as a potent antibiotic against *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris* and *H. pylori*. **Indian Journal of Applied & Pure Biology** 28 (2) : 213-215.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Effect of *Andrographis paniculata* on *Aspergillus* and *Rhizopus* species. *Agro-Summit 2013: Changing Scenario of Agriculture in Madhya Pradesh: Prospects & Challenges*. 171/13.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Allicin as a potent antibiotic against dermal infections. *International Conference on Recent Trends in Applied Sciences with Engineering Applications* (SCLS1.7) 57.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Effect of Stress on Glucose Metabolism. *National Seminar on Stress & Health Management*, 40.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2012) Anticancer drugs: Difficulties in development and usages. *National Seminar on Human Papilloma Virus and Control of Cervical Cancer-Current Scenario* (PP-8) 37.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2012) Evaluation and impact of anti-tuberculosis drug lines against an MDR - *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates *National Seminar on Environmental Conservation & Management*, 12.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A; Kalesharia, N (2011) Role of Genetic Research for Identification and Treatment of Cancer. *National Seminar On Emerging Trends In Research & Analysis for Sustainable Development*, 57.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2011) Growth inhibition of *E.coli*, *P.vulgaris* and *H. pylori* by Acillin. *National Seminar On Emerging Trends In Biodiversity & Environmental Conservation*, 29.
- Shrivastava, A.; **Garg, HK** (2015) Allicin as a dermal antibiotic against microbial infections. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 4(12) 1052-1056.
- Shrivastava, A.; **Garg, HK** (2014) Cytotoxic Potential of Andrographolide against Human Lung Adenocarcinoma Cell Lines - A 549. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, Newzeland 4(5): 9345-9348.